
Spatial Distribution and Temporal Change in Irrigated Area in Relation to the Hydrological Characteristics of the Gomti River Basin: A Case Study of Lucknow District.

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Abstract

This paper examines the spatial distribution of irrigated areas and irrigation sources at block level and also observes the temporal variations in the irrigated areas and sources of Lucknow district from 2000 to 2023; study is especially focused on the relationship between irrigation dynamics and the hydrological behaviour specifically ground water table of the Gomti River. Using block-wise data, the study outlines a huge decline in the total irrigated area in the district, and across the blocks, accompanied by a shift from surface water irrigation sources such as canals and ponds toward tube wells (groundwater-based irrigation). The spatial analysis shows significant reduction in irrigated areas in all 8 blocks except Mal block. The outcome of the study reveals growing hydrological stress on ground water table in the Gomti River basin, driven by urbanization, declining river discharge, decreased ground water recharge and overexploitation of groundwater resources.

Keywords: Irrigation, Groundwater, Urbanization, Agriculture, Gomti river, Canal.

Introduction

Irrigation is vital for agricultural productivity in the Indo-Gangetic plains, Lucknow district is the part of middle Ganga plain and drained by the Gomti river. Gomti River Basin is sub-basin of Ganga basin and plays a significant hydrological and socio-economic role in the district. The Lucknow District has historically relied on a combination of canal networks, ponds, wells and tubewells for irrigation. Over the past two decades, the district has undergone noticeable changes in irrigation patterns due to development, urbanization, infrastructural shifts, and groundwater depletion.

Irrigation is dependent on the availability of surface water and ground water level. Ground water level is closely interconnected with irrigation and also an important component of hydrological system. Continuous over exploitation for agricultural use can cause severe depletion in ground water, lowering water table, this may cause the increase in pumping cost. In areas under surface water irrigation such as canal may contribute in the ground water recharge by infiltration in the soil. Canal irrigation has positive impact on ground water but it has been seen that over the time canal irrigation has decreased and use of tube wells has risen.

This study analyses the spatial distribution and temporal changes in irrigation sources across the blocks of Lucknow District between 2000 and 2023, specially in context of the Gomti river basin.

Study Area: Lucknow is the district of state of Uttar Pradesh, having a rich heritage and cultural wealth in its history but most high tech and modern city of current era in Uttar Pradesh. Lucknow covers an area of 2565 sq. km. and has its geographical extension between the latitude 26° 30" N to 27° 10" N and longitude 80° 30" E to 81° 13" E. Gomti river traverses from the middle of the district. The Lucknow city is developed along both the banks of Gomti river. The agriculture, industry and culture have flourished around the Gomti river. District fall under the subtropical climate and faces three seasons clearly, winter, summer and monsoon. The

administrative division of district is in 8 blocks, namely Bakshi ka Talab, Mal, Chinhat, Kakori, Malihabad, Sarojani nagar, Mohanlalganj, and Gosaiganj. Initially the city has been the centre of administration along with agriculture, being an important occupation of people of the region. The district has grown as an urban centre and a long-term analysis of land use and land cover pattern shows that the agricultural land use is on continuous decline. There are three canals namely; Gomti feeder canal, Gomti right bank canal, Gomti left bank canal, which supply water to Lucknow district and other associated areas. These canals get their water supply from Gomti Barrage constructed on Gomti river in Lucknow. Gomti river enters Lucknow district from the north in Bakshi ka talab, forming boundary between Mal block and Bakshi ka Talab, Kakori and Chinhat and flow from the middle of Chinhat block and exit Lucknow through the Gosaiganj block.

Figure 1

Source: Prepared by ArcGIS Using SOI Data

Objective-

1. To observe the spatial distribution of major irrigation sources along the Gomti river in the Lucknow district from 2000-2023.
2. To compare temporal changes in the means of irrigation sources from 2000-2023.
3. To identify the high irrigation stressed and groundwater dependent areas.

Data Sources and Methodology: -

Data Sources- This study is based on the secondary data base of government and other authentic publications. The data of block-wise irrigated area of 1999-2000 and 2022-23 collected from the District Statistical Handbook, Lucknow. The ground water level data of 2023 at various ground water stations collected from the government website which is published by the Central Ground Water Board.

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Methodology: The data of block- wise irrigated areas and irrigation sources is compiled and tabulated in Microsoft Excel. Calculation of differences in changes in areas and number of sources, percentage of change, preparation of bar diagram and pie chart based on the available data has performed in Microsoft Excel.

Block	Canal	Tube well		Well	Ponds	Others	Total
		Government	Private				
1. Malihabad	2055	698	10110	0	28	22	12913
2. Mal	1409	2075	8301	79	27	28	11919
3. Bakshi-Ka-Talab	4095	2151	14732	31	20	180	21209
4. Kakori	3446	463	8794	0	10	72	12785
5. Chinhat	510	1072	5823	4	13	0	7422
6. Sarojaninagar	3096	725	15721	61	6	221	19830
7. Gosaiganj	7920	438	7597	0	22	0	15977
8. Mohanlalganj	6987	340	10783	0	10	0	18120
Total Rural	29518	7962	81861	175	136	523	120175
Total Urban	302	0	1336	0	0	31	1669
Total District	29820	7962	83197	175	136	554	121844

Source: District Statistical handbook

Table:1 Block-wise Actual Irrigated Area in hectares 1999-2000

In the year of 1999-2000 the total irrigated area was 121844 hectares by various means, and urban area contributed about 1669 ha. The largest irrigated area was under the means of private tubewell which was 83197 hectares and second largest of 29820 ha was done by means of canals. Gosaiganj, Mohanlalganj had about 7920 ha, 6987 ha area under the canal irrigation, Chinhat and Mal had lowest area under canal irrigation.

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Bakshi ka Talab area was the block which had largest irrigated area of 21209 ha and second largest area was under Sarojani Nagar had 19830 ha.

Block	Canal	Tube well		Well	Pond, Lake, Pool	Others	Total
		Government	Private				
1. Malihabad	1555	362	10018	0	0	0	11935
2. Mal	1569	498	11236	0	0	0	13303
3. Bakshi-Ka-Talab	2234	899	15474	0	3	0	18610
4. Kakori	3146	481	8384	0	0	0	12011
5. Chinhat	331	265	2248	0	0	0	2844
6. Sarojaninagar	1596	792	10548	0	0	0	12936
7. Gosaiganj	2869	204	9245	0	1	0	12319
8. Mohanlalganj	6306	366	10386	0	0	0	17058
Total Rural	19606	3867	77539	0	4	0	101016
Total Urban	96	105	1808	0	0	0	2009
Total District	19702	3972	79347	0	4	0	103025

Source: District Statistical handbook

Table:2 Block-wise Actual Irrigated Area in hectares 2022-23

In 2022-23 Total irrigated area in district is 103025 ha and urban irrigated area is 2009 ha, total canal irrigated area is 19702 ha. Total area under government tubewell and private tubewell is 3972 ha and 79347 ha respectively. Maximum area under irrigation by all means is 18610 ha in Bakshi ka Talab followed by Mohanlalganj (17058 ha). Lowest irrigated area is 2844 ha in Chinhat.

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Block	Canal	Tube well		Well	Ponds	Others	Total
		Government	Private				
1. Malihabad	-500	-336	-92	0	-28	-22	-978
2. Mal	160	-1577	2935	-79	-27	-28	1384
3. Bakshi-Ka-Talab	-1861	-1252	742	-31	-17	-180	-2599
4. Kakori	-300	18	-410	0	-10	-72	-774
5. Chinhat	-179	-807	-3575	-4	-13	0	-4578
6.Sarojaninagar	-1500	67	-5173	-61	-6	-221	-6894
7. Gosaiganj	-5051	-234	1648	0	-21	0	-3658
8.Mohanlalganj	-681	26	-397	0	-10	0	-1062
Total Rural	-9912	-4095	-4322	-175	-132	-523	-19159
Total Urban	-206	105	472	0	0	-31	340
Total District	-10118	-3990	-3850	-175	-132	-554	-18819

Source: District Statistical handbook

Table: 3 Difference in irrigated areas in hectare in between the year of 2000 and 2023

The analysis of the Table 3 this is apparent that total irrigated area is decreased by 18819 ha by all means of irrigation, largest decrease in total irrigated area by various means is noticed in Sarojaninagar block of 6894 ha, Chinhat (4578 ha), Gosaiganj (3658 ha), and canal irrigated area is decreased by 10118 ha. Largest area under canal irrigation of 5051 ha is decreased in Gosaiganj and followed by Bakshi ka Talab (1861ha), Sarojaninagar (1500 ha), Mohanlalganj (681) blocks. Total area under tube well irrigation also decreased by 3990 ha (government tube wells) and 3850 ha (private tube wells), and well irrigation is decreased by 175 ha, Ponds irrigation is 132 ha, and others is 554 ha. Total decrease in rural irrigated area is 19159 ha.

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Figure:2

Figure:3

Block	Length of canals (km)	State Tube Wells (No.)	Wells (No.)	Pumping Sets on Ground Water (No.)	Shallow Tube Well				Medium Tube Wells (No.)	Deep Tube Wells (No.)
					Electric Operated	Diesel Operated	Other	Total		
1. Malihabad	78	22	170	10	0	0	0	0	0	0
2. Mal	103	77	139	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
3. Bakshi-Ka-Talab	166	92	169	49	0	0	0	0	0	0
4. Kakori	90	34	88	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
5. Chinhat	24	53	125	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
6. Sarojaninagar	170	21	174	6	0	0	0	0	0	0
7. Gosaiganj	144	19	268	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
8. Mohanlalganj	187	23	279	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Rural	962	341	1412	92	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Urban	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total District	962	341	1412	92	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: District Statistical handbook

Table:4 Block- wise distribution of Sources of irrigation 1999-2000

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In 1999-2000 total length of canals in Lucknow was 962 km and all the 8 blocks had more or less area under canal irrigation, maximum area was existed under canal irrigation, highest length of canal was in Mohanlalganj followed by Sarojani nagar, Bakshi ka Talab, Gosaiganj and Mal over more than 100 km. There were 341 state tubewells, 1412 Wells and 92 Pumping sets on ground water were existed. Bakshi ka Talab had about maximum concentration of all the available sources of irrigation. Mohanlalganj and Gosaiganj had great density of well of 279 and 268 respectively. Chinhat lacked in the canal irrigation but had a good number of wells.

Table: 5 Block- wise distribution of Sources of Irrigation 2022-23

Block	Length of canals(km)	State Tube Wells (No.)	Wells(No.)	Pumping Sets on Ground Water (No.)	Shallow Tube Well				Medium Tube Wells (No.)	Deep Tube Wells (No.)
					Electric Operated	Diesel Operated	Ot her	Tot al		
1. Malihabad	78	27	10	10	373	2771	165	3309	148	35
2. Mal	103	76	2	0	496	3368	183	4047	65	63
3. Bakshi-Ka-Talab	166	98	19	16	277	5375	265	5917	182	82
4. Kakori	90	31	0	0	115	2976	121	3212	101	14
5. Chinhat	24	36	0	1	242	2429	148	2819	65	45
6. Sarojaninagar	170	26	0	2	132	5168	179	5479	86	27
7. Gosaiganj	144	20	8	0	130	5605	189	5924	78	15
8. Mohanlalganj	187	25	13	0	214	7927	195	8336	146	18
Total Rural	962	339	52	29	1979	35619	1445	39043	871	299
Total Urban	0	0	0	0	0	48	0	48	0	0
Total District	962	339	52	29	1979	35667	1445	39091	871	299

Source: District Statistical handbook

In the year of 2022-23 the canal length 962 km has not changed from previous decades and maximum length is in Mohanlalganj block. State tubewells are 339 which have reduced and wells remained only few in numbers, this is an enormous decrease from 1412 in the year of 2000 to 52 in the year of 2023, only Bakshi ka Talab and Mohanlalganj have wells in double digits 19 and 13 respectively.

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Figure:4

Figure:5

Table :6 Ground water level status of Lucknow district in 2023 yearly range*Source – Central ground water board*

Ground water Station	Observed Range of Water Level (mbgl)
Lu New Campus_1	-25.64 - 1
Mohanlalganj_2	-6.9 - -1.22
Rehman Khera_1	-36.11 - -12.23
Tejkishan Khera_1	-4.56 - 2.47
Vikasnagar_1	-46.28 - -41.09

Ground water level in Lucknow district is in critical status, this is apparent from the above table, that except the two ground water station of Mohanlalganj and Tejkishan Khera all other three ground water monitoring stations have recorded severe decline. The Gomti river is dependent on the ground water, the availability of ground water ensures the level of surface water also. Recently this has been observed that the severe exploitation of ground water for irrigation purposes has degraded the level of ground water table in Gomti river basin in Lucknow.

Result and Discussion-

(a) Status of Canal Irrigation

The data showing that the total length of canal has remained unchanged since 2000, which means there is no development or modernization in the canal irrigation network between two decades. Gomti River is continuously supplying the water to the canal system, but over the time reduced river discharge, siltation, and poor maintenance have negatively affected canal efficiency. Resultantly there is a sharp decline in the contribution of canal irrigation to total irrigated area, which can be observed by comparing the data.

(b) Decline of Traditional Wells and Pumping sets:

The analytical study of traditional open wells indicates that the irrigation from open wells is non- prevalent in current time as the number of open wells has declined from 1,412 to only 52, which reduced by 96 %, this is a huge downfall which reflects open wells are being unviable due to falling groundwater levels, urbanization and land conversion around all the blocks specially in Chinhat, Kakori, Sarojaninagar. The number of pumping sets decreased from only 92 in 1999–2000 to over 29 in 2022–23.

(c) Tube Well Expansion and Depth Intensification:

In 1999–2000, only 341 state tube wells existed but in 2022-23 it is reduced to 339. In 1999-2000 there were no shallow, medium, and deep tubewells but by 2022–23 there are multiple categories such as shallow, medium and deep tubewells' can be seen on the basis of mode of operation and depth of extraction. The number of shallow diesel (35667), electrically operated (1979), medium tube wells (871) and deep tube wells (299) has increased dramatically.

Hydrological Implications on Gomti river:

Seasonal flow reduction in Gomti river due to erratic monsoon pattern, and sedimentation have decreased canal discharge, lowered the surface irrigation potential. Currently, over- dependence on government and private tube wells has caused declining groundwater levels, especially in the blocks having higher percentage

of urbanization. Encroachment of wells and ponds have deteriorated the natural recharge systems, reducing baseflow to the Gomti river and their tributaries in Lucknow district. Rapid urbanization has transformed fertile agricultural land in other land use categories, and intensified the hydrological stress.

Conclusion:

The northern and central blocks (Bakshi-Ka-Talab, Malihabad, Mal) display the moderate irrigation sustainability, which is benefited from upper canal networks and also get water from Gomti floodplain. The southern and eastern blocks (Sarojaninagar, Gosaiganj, Chinhath) display severe decrease, due to urban encroachment, reduced infiltration and paved surface expansion. The shift from surface water irrigation sources to groundwater sources shows a hydrological transition driven by decreasing Gomti flow and over extraction. The overall study of spatial distribution of irrigation sources and irrigated areas under various irrigation sources clarifies that the total irrigated area in the district has decreased continuously and declining trend has been observed across the blocks but the traditional irrigation sources of surface water are on decline in Lucknow district due to various reasons. Now dependency on ground water has become significant and number of privately owned tubewells has increased which are extracting water from different depths. This extraction is burdening the ground water level in Gomti river basin which is on continuous decrease from past decades. Recent trends which emerged in agriculture are diesel-based mechanization and Electrification, reduced reliability of canal water, availability of private tube wells and pump sets, neglect of traditional recharge systems such as ponds and percolation wells. The decline of these wells also represents the loss of small-scale, sustainable water structures that once supported rural hydrology and river recharge.

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